

1 **Control of T-complex genes by human NOD2.**

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7 In a heterologous HEK293T system, wild-type human NOD2 could activate Tcte3 and repress Tcp112.
8 The NOD2 L1007fsinsC mutant found in patients with Crohn's Disease possessed similar transcriptional
9 control potential for T-complex proteins but displayed differential isoform control for some genes including
10 Tcte3.

11 Citations

12 1. Willison, K.R., Dudley, K. and Potter, J., 1986. Molecular cloning and sequence analysis of a
13 haploid expressed gene encoding t complex polypeptide 1. Cell, 44(5), pp.727-738.

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